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INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION

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The background of the lower half of the poster features a panoramic view of the Ottawa skyline. The CN Tower is the most prominent structure, standing tall on the right side. To its left, several modern high-rise buildings with glass facades are visible. In the foreground, the Ottawa River flows, with several white ferries and a small motorboat. The sky is a clear, light blue.

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PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE TRANSPORTATION AND STORAGE SERVICES MARKET IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article analyzes the issues of improving the organizational and economic mechanisms of the development of the transport and storage services market. Based on the analysis of world practice and national reforms, the existing problems, opportunities and effective solutions in the field are considered. Factors such as the development of transport and logistics infrastructure, the effective use of digital technologies and the expansion of public-private partnerships were highlighted as the main priorities of the mechanism.

Key words: transport and storage services, transport, integration, logistics system, modernization, economic competitiveness

In the process of globalization and integration taking place in the world, the importance of transport and storage services is increasing. According to the World Bank, the volume of world transport services in the structure of GDP is 4.3 trillion. US dollars (6.9%), 110 billion. tons of cargo and more than 1 trillion. passengers are transported per year, the number of employees employed in the transport complex is 100 million. people. The development of these sectors is carried out by the global transport and logistics system. The use of modern delivery technologies in the transport system allows saving the volume of material resources by 30% to 60%, as well as reducing the delivery costs of enterprises using transport services by approximately 30-35%. The market for logistics and storage services in the global economy is gaining strategic importance. In particular, this sector is receiving special attention in Uzbekistan in connection with the modernization of transport and communication infrastructure, increasing foreign trade turnover and improving the investment climate. It is important to improve organizational and economic mechanisms for effective organization of transportation and storage services, increase their competitiveness and improve service quality.

The transport complex, which performs the main "blood circulation" function in the effective development of the economies of world countries, is of particular importance. An effective transport system optimizes the movement of raw materials and products in the domestic market, while at the same time increasing the country's economic competitiveness in foreign trade and accelerating the integration processes into the world market. In general, the large-scale development of the country and the high pace of interregional economic relations are directly related to the effective functioning of the transport infrastructure in a broad sense. The main objects of the transport infrastructure of Uzbekistan include highways, railways, waterways, metro, airports, bridges, tunnels, overpasses, contact lines, train stations and stations, objects of the communication, navigation and vehicle traffic control system, and other similar

buildings, structures, devices and equipment that ensure the functioning of the transport complex. Unlike transport infrastructure, the transport system is directly related to the functioning of the country's economy as a whole.

The transport system is not only the road network (i.e., transport infrastructure), but also its technical and management part. However, the development of transport infrastructure plays a key role in creating a unified transport complex of the country. The development of the transport network can be based on the structure of the transport complex, which includes the following transport system and infrastructure.

Transport is a separate, unified system in the economic sector, and when we study the issues related to the effective development of its activities, we form a hierarchical picture of the problems existing in the sector. As is known, in accordance with the law of hierarchy, each stage in the system performs the function of a managing and managed entity with those below and above it. Recognizing that a hierarchical approach is the most optimal option for ensuring the efficiency of the transport system, conducting scientific research in this area is becoming increasingly relevant today. In a hierarchical system, from the point of view of the implementation of a certain task at each stage, it is natural that there is functional and structural differentiation in it. From the point of view of the reception, processing and use of a large amount of information in the system, it is advisable for it to have a hierarchical structure. In this case, generalized information is provided for use by lower stages. Existing problems in the transport system are one of the factors that hinder the growth of the country's economy. Therefore, it is advisable to consider these problems separately: – to more fully meet the growing needs of the economy as its sectors expand and the population grows; – to provide high-quality services to meet consumer needs; – to develop measures to minimize transportation costs at the cost of goods; – to achieve high efficiency of the transport system.

The logistics services market in Uzbekistan has been growing significantly in recent years. In 2024, almost 60 percent of the country's foreign trade was carried out by road, rail and air transport. At the same time, the demand for storage services is also growing sharply.

The market for transportation and storage services has a number of structural and organizational problems. In particular:

- Incomplete development of logistics infrastructure;
- Lack of storage warehouses and their technical equipment;
- Inadequate competitive environment among transport organizations;
- Non-integration of information systems.

These problems lead to low quality of service in the sector and insufficient operational efficiency. Therefore, the introduction of effective organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of this sector, in particular, modernization of infrastructure, digitalization, expansion of public-private partnerships and increasing human resources potential are among the priority areas:

- Modernization of infrastructure. The quality and efficiency of service will be significantly improved by building warehouses and logistics centers and equipping them

with modern equipment. Encouraging the participation of the private sector is of great importance in this.

- Improving digitalization and data exchange. The transparency and efficiency of the logistics chain will be ensured by digitizing logistics processes, introducing online tracking and management platforms, as well as expanding EDI (Electronic Data Interchange) systems.

- Public-Private Partnership (PPP) Implementation of public-private partnership models in attracting investment to infrastructure projects, in particular, the provision of guarantees and incentives by the state in the construction of logistics hubs and warehouses, is an important factor.

- Increasing the capacity of personnel Training of personnel with competitive and modern knowledge in the field, their retraining and upgrading their qualifications based on international experiences is an important component of the organizational and economic mechanism.

The analysis described above shows that the existing problems in the market of transportation and storage services are a serious obstacle to its stable and effective development. In particular, the insufficient development of the infrastructure, the low level of technical equipment, the limited competitive environment and the insufficient integration of information systems are the main factors that reduce the quality of services and economic efficiency.

In general, the consistent and effective implementation of the above measures will help to form a modern, competitive and integrated logistics services market in Uzbekistan, which will contribute to the deeper integration of the national economy into global trade chains.

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